

Enabling comprehensive optogenetic studies of mouse hearts by simultaneous opto-electrical panoramic mapping and stimulation

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Abstract

To advance exploitation of the unique research opportunities offered by cardiac optogenetics, we developed a panoramic opto-electrical measurement (POEMS) system for mouse hearts. The core of the experimental platform is composed of 294 optical fibers and 64 electrodes that form a cup which embraces the entire ventricular surface of mouse hearts and enables straightforward 'drop&go' experimentation. The flexible assignment of fibers and electrodes to recording or stimulation tasks permits a precise tailoring of experiments to the specific requirements of individual optogenetic constructs thereby avoiding spectral congestion. We hereby provide the reader with a brief step-by-step protocol of the experimental workflow using mouse hearts.

The protocol includes the most critical steps of performing a POEMS experiment with a mouse heart including heart excision, mounting, perfusion and staining. Details with regards to the solutions used, data acquisition and data analysis can be found in the method section of the article.

Procedure

Step-1: Preparation of the solutions and quality check of the Langendorff system

- Freshly prepare the Krebs-Henseleit buffer without Ca^{2+} .
- Bubble the solution with a mixture of 95% O_2 /5% CO_2 for 20 minutes.
- Gently add CaCl_2 from a 1mol/L stock solution, into the Krebs-Henseleit buffer to reach a final concentration of 1.2mmol/L.
- Filter the Krebs-Henseleit buffer using a 20-micron nylon filter to remove any potential particles within the solution.
- Separate the filtered solution into two halves (solution A and B).
- Place solution A into a freezer at -20°C for rapid cooling (*15-20 minutes*).
- Add I-blebbistatin from a stock solution (30 mmol/L) to solution B to obtain a final concentration of 15mmol/L (*1:2000 dilution*).
- Maintain solution B under constant bubbling with 95% O_2 /5% CO_2 (*for further use on the Langendorff apparatus*) and protect from light.
- Turn on the peristaltic pump and the thermostatic circulator to progressively fill the Langendorff system with solution B.
- The flow rate is adjusted to 3.5 ml/min and the solution temperature to 37°C .
- A separate gassed perfusion system used for heart cannulation is filled with cooled solution A and the flow through the system with the cannula attached is verified.
- A temperature controlled (4°C) titanium dish used for immersing the heart after excision is filled with cooled solution A.
- Two additional 50 ml beakers are filled with 25 ml of the remaining cooled solution A.

Step-2: Preparation of the animal and heart excision

- Determine the weight of the mouse.
- Place the mouse into an anesthesia induction chamber with 4-5% isoflurane and an oxygen flow of 2L/min and add eye ointment.
- Once the animal is properly anesthetized, perform an intraperitoneal injection of unfractionated heparin (1000IU) and maintain the anesthesia using a facemask and an isoflurane delivery at 2-2.5% with 2L/min O_2 .
- After 5 further minutes, cervical dislocation is performed.

- The absence of the toe-pinch reflex is verified and thoracotomy performed.
- The heart is carefully excised, gently washed in the beakers containing ice-cold solution A and finally immersed in the temperature-controlled titanium dish containing solution A.
- Lung residues and pericardium are removed to obtain a clean preparation.

Step-3: Cannulation of the heart and mounting on the POEMS system

- The heart is cannulated through the aorta and cannulation secured with two sutures
- Perfusion with gassed, ice-cold solution A is turned on to wash the coronary vessels.
- The heart is transferred to the Langendorff system and perfusion with solution B is immediately started.
- Correct placement of the heart in the POEMS system is achieved by first centering the heart in the cavity of one container half with the LAD being aligned with the left edge of the container. Then, the second container half is slid over the heart and automatically secured in the correct position by built in guidance structures and magnets. The entire mounting process last less than 1 min.
- During warming up of the heart to 37°C, continuous monitoring of electrical signals at multiple sites offers insights as to the stability and quality of the whole-heart preparation.
- After an equilibration period of 15-20 minutes, the preparation reaches steady state and experiments can be started.

Step-4: Staining with voltage sensitive dyes (where applicable)

- To obtain appropriate staining with Di-8-ANEPPS, 1 ml of staining solution containing 135 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ of the dye in solution B is injected into the perfusion upstream of the cannula during 30 seconds.
- POEMS experiments are started 10 minutes after the injection.